

Agronomic data for test entries. La Plata, Argentina, 1987.^a

Designation	Alkaline							Saline							Normal						
	Scores			Germination (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)	Scores			Germination (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)	Scores			Germination (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)
	VP	RP	PA					VP	RP	PA					VP	RP	PA				
Gz1368-5-2	6	4	5	15	59	17	175	6	5	5	30	67	19	—	6	3	5	20	79	19	165
Gz1368-5-54	6	4	5	5	62	17	168	6	4	4	20	65	17	166	6	3	5	20	82	21	165
IR10154-117-2-3-3-3	6	5	6	10	47	16	152	5	4	6	35	54	18	173	6	3	5	30	71	18	178
IR10206-29-2-1	6	6	6	5	57	18	—	5	4	4	20	72	29	—	5	2	4	30	84	21	168
IR19392-33-3	6	7	6	10	42	15	178	6	5	7	10	—	—	—	6	4	5	10	72	18	164
IR19743-25-2-2-3-1	5	5	5	35	51	16	148	5	4	5	10	60	18	162	6	4	5	5	70	17	174
IR28	6	5	4	35	56	18	152	5	3	5	30	62	18	151	6	4	5	10	90	21	161
IR31375-3-3-3	5	4	5	15	72	20	178	4	3	8	20	—	—	169	7	2	6	30	92	21	—
IR32307-107-3-2-2	4	4	4	50	56	22	173	4	3	7	20	—	—	165	6	3	6	30	78	21	—
IR32429-47-3-2-2	4	4	4	40	60	17	154	3	3	6	25	—	—	147	6	4	5	20	65	20	174
IR37379-20-1-2-1-1	5	5	7	55	45	16	141	5	4	7	20	50	16	131	6	2	5	40	56	14	169
IR8238-B-B-57-2-1	5	5	5	30	73	19	174	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	6	2	6	40	87	22	—
KS-282	4	4	4	50	61	19	172	5	5	7	20	—	—	—	6	2	5	30	80	21	178
IR9129-209-2-2-2-3	6	5	6	55	53	18	163	5	4	6	50	64	19	160	6	3	5	30	72	20	174
<i>Local checks</i>																					
Itape P.A.	4	4	5	40			153	5	2	3	50			164							
Yerua P.A.	5	3	5	35			153	4	2	3	30			153							
H198-1-3-2-3-1	3	2	4	60			165	3	2	3	15			134							
H198-8-1-2-1	4	2	4	10			161	3	2	3	15			160							
H238-5-1	3	2	3	30			164	3	2	3	10			146							
H238-20-1-1	4	2	4	25			162	3	2	3	20			138							
H238-47-1	was not seeded							3	2	3	20			152							
H238-82-2-1	3	2	3	30			169	was not seeded													
H175	4	2	3	45			159	was not seeded													

^a VP = vegetative phase, RP = reproductive phase, PA = phenotypic acceptability.

normal soil 20 Oct, at 1 row/entry and 25-cm spacing. Germination began 17 Oct, the test plot was irrigated 15 d later. Agronomic data were collected each 15 d and subsumed into values for vegetative phase, reproductive phase, and phenotypic acceptability (see table).

All exotic lines were affected adversely, mainly by temperature and photoperiod. Climate-adapted local checks showed the best performance under both treatments.

Entries showed more tolerance in the reproductive than in the vegetative

phase. More plants died during the vegetative phase.

Plant height and panicle length correlated strongly with soil problems and were more affected by alkalinity than by salinity. □

Extragenic basis of salt tolerance in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

M. S. Sajjad and M. A. Awan, Nuclear Institute for Agriculture and Biology (NIAB), Faisalabad, Pakistan

NIAB Rice-1 has been found to be relatively salt tolerant and Basmati 370 to be relatively salt sensitive. To clarify the extragenic basis of salt tolerance, we made reciprocal crosses between the two genotypes. The F₁ hybrids and the parents were transplanted at 45 d after seeding on nonsaline and saline sodic field basins. Salinization of the field basins was accomplished using four commercial salts of MgCl, NaCl,

CaCl₂, and Na₂SO₄ in a 1:4:5:10 equivalent ratio.

The experiment was laid out in a complete randomized block design

with three replications. Interrow and intrarow spacing was 20 cm. Data for yield and yield components were recorded on 10 plants/replication.

Inheritance of yield and yield components under normal and saline sodic soils.^a Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Parent or F ₁ combination	Nonsaline soil ^b				Saline soil ^c			
	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Yield (g/plant)	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Yield (g/plant)
Basmati 370	139.8 b	13.8 b	36.7 d	13.5 c	126.8 b	9.0 c	25.0 c	9.0 c
Basmati 370/NIAB Rice-1	162.8 a	21.6 a	39.7 b	17.0 b	143.9 a	18.0 a	34.8 b	14.0 b
NIAB Rice-1/Basmati 370	159.2 a	20.4 a	42.9 b	18.4 ab	144.9 a	19.0 a	34.1 b	12.9 b
NIAB Rice-1	143.8 b	19.0 a	59.0 a	20.4 a	122.7 b	15.6 b	51.4 a	17.1 a

^aIn a column, values followed by identical letters are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bpH 7.6, EC 3.0 dS/m, SAR 9.0. ^cpH 8.7, EC 6.2 dS/m, SAR 20.0.

Productive tillers/plant, flag leaf area, and yield/plant of Basmati 370 and NIAB Rice-1 in both environments differed significantly (see table). Plant height did not differ. Performance of the F₁s of Basmati 370/NIAB Rice-1 and NIAB Rice-1/Basmati 370 did not

differ. The F₁s showed heterosis over Basmati 370 for all the traits studied. However, true heterobeltiosis was observed only for plant height.

These results indicate the absence of any extragenic basis of salt tolerance, at least for these two genotypes. □

TTB15-1 is 90 cm tall with intermediate tillering ability and 114-125 d duration. It is awnless, medium-grained, with fully exerted panicles. The 1,000-grain weight is 22.0 g. It has nonglutinous endosperm with translucent white kernels and acceptable cooking quality.

TTB15-1 is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, brown planthopper, and whitebacked planthopper but susceptible to blast. It is resistant to shattering.

In eight transplanting trials in Karimganj and Titabar, yield was 8-36.8% higher than that of check varieties (see table). In on-farm trials, its yield advantage was higher because a low yielding local traditional ahu variety was used as the check. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Release of new rice cultivar Jasmine 85 in USA

C. N. Bollich, Agricultural Research Service (ARS), USDA, Route 7, Box 999, Beaumont, Texas 77713, USA

The release of Jasmine 85, a new long-grain rice cultivar, was announced by ARS, U.S. Department of Agriculture and the agricultural experiment stations of Texas, Mississippi, Arkansas, and Louisiana.

Jasmine 85 (IR841) derives from the IRRI cross IR262/Khao Dawk Mali

105. IR262 was from the cross Peta *3/ Taichung Native 1.

Jasmine 85 is an aromatic (scented) rice possessing the flavor and aroma of fragrant rices of Thailand. Average amylose content is 17% and alkali spreading value 6.5. This characterizes Jasmine 85 as a low-amylose, low-gelatinization-temperature type similar to Thai fragrant rices. Typically, cooked grains of Jasmine 85, like those of the Thai fragrant rices, are soft and cohesive with the cooked kernels tending to cling together. □

Medium-duration Taichung Sen Yu 285 released in Sichuan as Chuan Mi 2

Deng Jutao, Luo Wenzhi, Yuan Zuolian, and Yin Guoda, Rice Research Institute (RRI), Sichuan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Luzhou, Sichuan, China

Taichung Sen Yu 285, an International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) entry from Taiwan, evaluated in Sichuan since 1983—at RRI for 3 yr and in regional provincial tests for 2 yr—was released in Mar 1989 as Chuan Mi 2 for cultivation in Sichuan.

Mean grain yield over 3 yr in RRI trials was 7.6 t/ha, 7% higher than the local check (see table). In the 1986-87 regional test for grain quality, mean grain yield was 7.4 t/ha, 6% higher than the local check. In 1988 Adaptive Research Trials in three counties, mean grain yield was 7.4 t/ha, 7% higher than the local check.

Chuan Mi 2 is a semidwarf (90-95 cm), heavy-tillering rice with 135-140 d duration. Grain is medium slender, fine and white, with 3.6% amylose and 10.73% protein content. It has 73% milling recovery and good cooking quality.

TTB15-1, a promising rice variety for Assam

T. Ahmed, R. K. S. M. Barua, K. C. Sarma, G. R. Das, K. K. Sarma, D. K. Barua, U. Kalita, P. K. Pathak, and A. K. Pathak, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Assam Agricultural University, Titabar 785630, Assam, India

TTB15-1 is a medium-duration variety suitable for transplanted ahu (autumn) season in Assam under rainfed conditions. The variety was developed at RARS from IR24/CR44-118-1 and has been recommended for cultivation in relatively flood-free medium-altitude ricelands.

Grain yield and duration of TTB15-1 in trials in Assam, India, 1984-88.

Year	Location	Growing condition	TTB15-1		Check			
			Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Increase over check (%)
1984	Titabar	Ahu	4.3	115	Ch 63	3.8	111	15
1984	Titabar	Ahu	3.6	123	TTB2-6-1-1	3.2	134	14
1985	Karimganj	Ahu	2.2	116	IR50	1.9	111	17
1986	Karimganj	Ahu	2.8	114	IR50	2.2	103	32
1987	Karimganj	Ahu	2.8	118	IR50	2.6	111	8
1987	Titabar	Ahu	2.9	124	TTB2-6-1-1	2.4	132	20
1987	Titabar	Sali	4.0	124	Ratna	2.9	116	34
1988	Titabar	Ahu	5.5	125	Ratna	4.0	128	37
	Mean		3.5	120		2.9		23
<i>On-farm trial</i>								
1986	Gelapukhuri	Ahu	2.7	125	Takuguni	1.4	117	97
1988	Gelapukhuri	Ahu	4.2	123	Takuguni	1.9	114	125